

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369274134>

New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous

Preprint · March 2023

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925

CITATIONS

0

1 author:

Henry Garrett

373 PUBLICATIONS 6,374 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Metric Dimension in fuzzy(neutrosophic) Graphs [View project](#)

Number Graphs And Numbers [View project](#)

New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous

Henry Garrett · Independent Researcher · Department of Mathematics ·
DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com · Manhattan, NY, USA

1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Stable-Neighbor pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : N(E_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : N(E_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : N(V_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : N(V_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Neighbor). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $C(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it's either of

Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; a Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic

SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic
rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic
coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic
cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S
of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its
Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new
SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and Neutrosophic
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut
for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform,
and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature
review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the
significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other
SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions
are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with
different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical
aspect of this ongoing research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to
figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special
case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them.
Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells.
These types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all
officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and
"Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's
Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues
to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are
posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions
and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then
 δ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum
cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic)
cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are
 $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first
Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds
if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is a
maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic
cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic
cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are:
 $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$;
and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression,
holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds
if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic"
version of a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . Since there's more ways to get type-results to
make a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor more understandable. For the sake of having
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a
"SuperHyperStable-Neighbor ". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are
assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the
usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . It's redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor
if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, "The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges,
HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph"

with the key points, “The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet”, “The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints”. To get structural examples and instances, I’m going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . It’s the main. It’ll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there’s a need to have all SuperHyperStable-Neighbor until the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then it’s officially called a “SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” but otherwise, it isn’t a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a “SuperHyperStable-Neighbor ”. These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, there’s a need to “redefine” the notion of a “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” and a “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor ”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there’s the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s redefined “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor are redefined to a “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” if the intended Table holds. It’s useful to define “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there’s more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are “Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite”, and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel” if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” where it’s the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor .] SuperHyperStable-Neighbor . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it’s a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It’s SuperHyperPath if it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it’s SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it’s SuperHyperStar it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it’s SuperHyperBipartite it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it’s SuperHyperMultiPartite it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it’s a SuperHyperWheel if it’s only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, The “specific” cells and “specific group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and intended properties between “specific” cells and “specific group” of cells

are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, it’s useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In the future research, the foundation will be based on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor or the strongest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, called SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and the strongest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Neighbor but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer’s attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer’s attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as “new groups”. Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I’ve found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. Thus it’s another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the “Cancer’s Recognition”. Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it’s the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy

and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognition" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances' styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called " SuperHyperStable-Neighbor" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperStable-Neighbor or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Neighbor but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the " amount of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor" of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the "amount of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor" based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the "Cancer's Recognition" in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It's motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled "SuperHyperGraphs". Thus it motivates us to define different types of " SuperHyperStable-Neighbor" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor" on "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, "Cancer's Recognition", more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, are figured out in sections “SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Stable-Neighbor to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “ SuperHyperStable-Neighbor”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “ SuperHyperStable-Neighbor”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [132]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [132]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [132]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [132]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [132]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [132]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [132]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [132]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [132]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.1, p.1). 347

Let X be a Stable-Neighbor of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$. 348
349

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.2, p.2). 350

Let X be a Stable-Neighbor of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.5, p.2). 351
352

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 353
354

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 355
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 356
357
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 358
359
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 360
361
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 362
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 363

$$(vii) \sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n); \quad 364$$

$$(viii) \sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, \quad (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'); \quad 365$$

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$. 366

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets. 367-376

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.7, p.3). 377-378

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 379-382

(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 383

(ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 384

(iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 385

(iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 386-387

(v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 388-389

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 390-391

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 392-393

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.7, p.3). 394

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 395-396

$$(i) 1 \otimes x = x; \quad 397$$

$$(ii) x \otimes y = y \otimes x; \quad 398$$

$$(iii) x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z; \quad 399$$

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [132], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 432
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 433
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 434
435
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 436
437
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 438
439

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities. 440
441
442

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 443
444

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable. 445
446

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. 447
448

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; 449
450
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; 451
452
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; 453
454
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 455
456
457
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 458
459
460
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 461
462
463

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) 464
465

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold: 464
465
466

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 467

- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 468
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 469
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 470
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 471
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 472
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 473
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 474
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 475
476

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 477

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 478

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 479
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 480
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 481
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 482
483

Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 484
(Ref. [132], Definition 5.3, p.7). 485

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have 486

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 487
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 488
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 489
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 490

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [132], Definition 5.4, p.7). 491
492

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 493
494

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : N(E_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : N(E_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : N(V_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : N(V_i) \text{ is Stable};$$

$$\text{and } |V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Neighbor).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;

(vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** if it's either of
 Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic
 re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and
 Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
 Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;

(vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial** if
 it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic
 re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and
 Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum
 Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Extreme power is corresponded to
 its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial** if
 it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic
 re-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and
 Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the
 maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that
 they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; and the Neutrosophic
 power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor).
 Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

(i) an δ -**SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperStable-Neighbor such that either of the following expressions hold for
 the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the
 Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor** is a Neutrosophic kind of
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor such that either of the following
 Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of
 SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta.$$

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. 621
 And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic** 622
 δ -SuperHyperDefensive. 623

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, there's a need to 624
 "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices 625
 and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. 626
 In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 627

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 628
 $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 629

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's 630
 more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more 631
 understandable. 632

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 633
 $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) 634
 holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, 635
 SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and 636
 SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic** 637
SuperHyperCycle, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic** 638
SuperHyperBipartite, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and 639
Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds. 640

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic 641
 SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a 642
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor more Neutrosophically understandable. 643

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, there's a need to 644
 "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor". The 645
 SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the 646
 letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to 647
 assign to the values. 648

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. It's redefined a 649
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if the Table (3) holds. 650

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

4 Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Neutrosophic event).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Any Neutrosophic k -subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Neutrosophic subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic event**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Neutrosophic Independent).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. s Neutrosophic k -events $A_i, i \in I$ is called **Neutrosophic s -independent** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Neutrosophic k -events of A and B is called **Neutrosophic independent**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Neutrosophic Variable).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Any k -function Stable-Neighbor like E is called **Neutrosophic k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Stable-Neighbor like E is called **Neutrosophic Variable**.

The notion of independent on Neutrosophic Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Neutrosophic Expectation).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Expectation** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Neutrosophic Crossing). 679

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. A Neutrosophic number is called **Neutrosophic Crossing** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Crossing criteria** 680
681
682
683

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let m and n propose special Stable-Neighbor. Then with $m \geq 4n$, 684
685
686

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Neutrosophic random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Neutrosophic independently with probability Stable-Neighbor $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$. 687
688
689
690

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Neutrosophic number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Neutrosophic Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have: 691

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□ 692

Theorem 4.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$. 693
694
695
696
697

Proof. Form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseNeighborive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. 698
699
700
701
702
703
704

Theorem 4.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$. 705
706
707
708

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Draw a SuperHyperUnit 709
710

SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Neutrosophic number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseNeighborive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n-1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n-1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k-n)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. $\square$

Proposition 4.9. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let X be a nonnegative Neutrosophic Variable and t a positive real number. Then*

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &\geq \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Stable-Neighbor (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.*

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k+1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Neutrosophic Variable for this Neutrosophic Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = (n \text{ choose } k+1)(1-p)^{(k+1)\text{choose}2}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$(n \text{ choose } k+1) \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1-p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p(k+1)\text{choose}2}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $n e^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Neutrosophic Variance).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Variance** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let X_n be a Neutrosophic Variable in a probability Stable-Neighbor (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
 Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$
 in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that
 $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$
 when $X_n = 0$. □

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For
 $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for
 which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values
 $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
 Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. As in the proof of related
 Theorem, the result is straightforward. □

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let
 f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

- (i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
 or
- (ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* .

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
 Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. □

Definition 4.17. (Neutrosophic Threshold).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let P be a monotone property of
 SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a
Neutrosophic Threshold for P is a function $f(n)$ such that:

- (i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,
- (ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Neutrosophic Balanced).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let F be a fixed Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a
 copy of F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Neutrosophic Balanced**.

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. Let F be a nonempty
 balanced Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l
 SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F
 as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$.
 Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 4.20. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

831

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

832

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

833

834

835

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

836

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

837

838

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

839

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=2}^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

840

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

841

842

Figure 5. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

843

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

844

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

845

846

847

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

848

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

849

850

Figure 6. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

851

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

852

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

853

854

855

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} = \\
 &\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

856

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

857

858

Figure 7. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 9. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

859

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

860

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

861

862

863

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} = \\
 & \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

864

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

865

866

Figure 10. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\
 &= \{E_1\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_{i=1,6}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^6. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{V_{i=4,5,6,9,10}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

Figure 11. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 13. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

Figure 14. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_5, V_6\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_1}, V_{E_2}, V_{E_3}, V_{E_4}, V_{E_5}, V_{E_6}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= bz^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

Figure 16. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

891

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\ &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_6\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^6. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\ &= \{V_{E_1}, V_{E_2}, V_{E_3}, V_{E_4}, V_{E_5}, V_{E_6}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= bz^6. \end{aligned}$$

892

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

893

894

895

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\ &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_6\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^6. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\ &= \{V_{E_1}, V_{E_2}, V_{E_3}, V_{E_4}, V_{E_5}, V_{E_6}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= bz^6. \end{aligned}$$

896

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

897

898

Figure 17. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 18. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{12}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{12}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_i}\}_{i=1}^{12}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= bz^{12}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_i}^{\text{INTERNAL SuperHyperVERTICES}}\}_{i=1}^{10}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= bz^{10}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 20. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 905
906
907

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\ = \{E_1, E_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\ = \{ \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 908
909
910

Figure 21. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

911

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=2}^5. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_i}\}_{i=2}^5. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= bz^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

912

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

913

914

915

916

917

918

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

919

920

921

922

923

924

925

926

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z

Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor.

Proposition 4.24. *Assume a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Neutrosophic number of type-result-R-Stable-Neighbor has, the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality, is the Neutrosophic cardinality of*

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Neutrosophic type-result-R-Stable-Neighbor with the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. *Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Is a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Neighbor. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Neighbor is the cardinality of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor since neither amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of

a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality indicates that these Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Neutrosophic lower bound in the term of Neutrosophic sharpness. In other words, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Neutrosophic structure of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor decorates the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Neutrosophic connections so as this Neutrosophic style implies different versions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Neutrosophic bound is to have the maximum Neutrosophic groups of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have perfect Neutrosophic connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph arising from its Neutrosophic properties taken

from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, then there's no Neutrosophic connection. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic existence of one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no Neutrosophic effect to talk about the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Since at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Neutrosophic background of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge but at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices make the Neutrosophic version of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Neutrosophic setting of non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Neutrosophic adjective for the initial Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Neutrosophic appearance of the loop Neutrosophic version of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and this Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Neutrosophic adjective "loop" on the basic Neutrosophic framework engages one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Neutrosophic setting. With these Neutrosophic bases, on a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor has the Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor has the Neutrosophic cardinality at least a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor since either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Neutrosophic usage of this Neutrosophic framework and even more there's no Neutrosophic connection inside or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Neutrosophic contradiction with the term "Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor" since the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality never happens for this Neutrosophic style of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Neutrosophic connection inside as mentioned in first Neutrosophic case in the forms of drawback for this selected Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Comes up. This Neutrosophic case implies having the Neutrosophic style of on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style on the every Neutrosophic elements of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that some Neutrosophic amount of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style. The Neutrosophic cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

But the lower Neutrosophic bound is up. Thus the minimum Neutrosophic cardinality of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality ends up the Neutrosophic discussion. The first Neutrosophic term refers to the Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClass of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style amid some amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. This Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel proposes a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has only some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from one

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Neutrosophic amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The Neutrosophic cardinality of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Neutrosophic case is occurred in the minimum Neutrosophic situation. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices taken from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as used Neutrosophic background in the Neutrosophic terms of worst Neutrosophic case and the common theme of the lower Neutrosophic bound occurred in the specific Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are Neutrosophic free-quasi-triangle. 951
952
953
954
955

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Then every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has at least no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Neutrosophic style-R-Stable-Neighbor. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor but with slightly differences in the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality amid those

Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Neutrosophic cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Let $Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

But with the slightly differences,

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \stackrel{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ for all Neutrosophic intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Neutrosophic optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is either

has the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor where the Neutrosophic completion of the Neutrosophic incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literally, a Neutrosophic embedded R-Stable-Neighbor. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality and they're Neutrosophic SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Neutrosophic style of the embedded Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. The interior types of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices pose the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Thus Neutrosophic exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and in Neutrosophic SuperHyperRelation with the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor, there's the usage of exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. The Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor with the inclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor has two titles. a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor and its corresponded quasi-maximum Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Neutrosophic number, there's a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor with that quasi-maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, then the Neutrosophic quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbors for all Neutrosophic numbers less than its Neutrosophic corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbors acted on the all possible used formations of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Neutrosophic number. This Neutrosophic number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Stable-Neighbors. 1028
 Let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}$ be a 1029
 Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and a Neutrosophic 1030
 Stable-Neighbor. Then 1031

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor is 1032
 re-formalized and redefined as follows. 1033

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal 1034
 technical definition for the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor. 1035

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Neutrosophic 1036
 Stable-Neighbor poses the upcoming expressions. 1037

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1038

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

And then,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}, \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}, \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ \{ S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's, literarily, another name for “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Neighbor” but, precisely, it's the generalization of “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Neighbor” since “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Neighbor” happens “Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality arise

from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, 1055
 “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Neighbor”, and “Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor” are up. 1056

Thus, let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and 1057
 $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic 1058
 SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor and the new terms are 1059
 up. 1060

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1061

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1062

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1063

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure, 1064

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\mid N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor** $C(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge amid some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor** is related to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Neighbor**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor. There isn't only less than two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Neutrosophic free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Neutrosophic on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Neutrosophic stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor amid those obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Neighbor if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Neutrosophic numbers of those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge excluding excluding more than r distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Since it doesn't have **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor. Since it **doesn't do** the Neutrosophic procedure such that such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, titled its Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Neutrosophic procedure"]. There's only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Neutrosophic pairs are titled Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Neutrosophic R-Stable-Neighbor only contains all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from the unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Stable-Neighbor, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{NeutrosophicCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{NeutrosophicCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

1141

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

1142

1143

1144

1145

1146

1147

1148

1149

1150

1151

1152

1153

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

1154

1155

1156

1157

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic

1158

1159

SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

1160

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Neighbor**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

1161

1162

1163

1164

1165

1166

1167

1168

1169

1170

1171

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor,

1172

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor, not:

1173

1174

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-NeighborSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

1175

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Quasi-Stable-Neighbor} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\,Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Quasi-Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\,Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,R-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,R-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

1176

1177

1178

“Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor”

1179

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

1180

Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor,

1181

is only and only

1182

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Quasi-Stable-Neighbor} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\,Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Quasi-Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\,Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,R-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,R-Quasi-Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

1183

5 The Neutrosophic Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

1184

1185

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

1186

1187

Proposition 5.1. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then*

1188

1189

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Stable-Neighbor} \\
&= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{NSHG}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= z^{|E_{NSHG}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,V-Stable-Neighbor} \\
&= \{V_{E_i}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{NSHG}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\,V-Stable-Neighbor\,SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= bz^{|E_{NSHG}|}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Neighbor} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{NSHG}|}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Neighbor\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= z^{|E_{NSHG}|}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Neighbor} \\
 &= \{V_{E_i}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{NSHG}|}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Neighbor\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= bz^{|E_{NSHG}|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Example (16.5)

1203

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\lfloor \frac{E_{NSHG} \rfloor}{3}}, V_{\lfloor \frac{E_{NSHG} \rfloor}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1204

1205

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. □

1206

1207

1208

Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

1209

1210

1211

1212

Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

1213

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.7)

Then

1214

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_i}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{NSHG}|}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= bz^{|E_{NSHG}|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1215

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 &CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

1216

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 &E_2, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1217

1218

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.9)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{\{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \}, \\
 &= \{\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Neighbor could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Example (16.11)

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E). Then

1252
1253

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor}} \\
 &= \{ \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \} \}, \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Neighbor SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1254

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

1255

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1256
1257

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Neighbor could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

1258
1259
1260
1261
1262
1263

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

1264
1265
1266
1267

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

1268
1269

Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

1270
1271
1272
1273
1274
1275

Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

1276
1277

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Neighbor} & \\ = \{ \} & \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Neighbor\ SuperHyperPolynomial} & \\ = 0z^0. & \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Neighbor} & \\ = \{ \{ One\ From\ Every\ MATCHING\ SuperHyperVertices \} \}, & \\ = \{ \} & \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Neighbor\ SuperHyperPolynomial} & \\ = 0z^0. & \end{aligned}$$

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Example (16.13)

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Neighbor could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperStable-Neighbor proposes some longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in the Neutrosophic Example (16.15)

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

1295

1296

For the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, some general results are introduced.

1297

1298

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

1299

1300

Corollary 6.2. Assume Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Then

1301

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable – Neighbor} = \\ & \left\{ \text{the SuperHyperStable – Neighbor of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \right. \\ & \quad \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \quad \text{SuperHyperStable – Neighbor} \\ & \quad \left. | \text{Neutrosophic cardinality among those SuperHyperStable – Neighbor.} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

1302

1303

1304

Corollary 6.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and SuperHyperStable-Neighbor coincide.

1305

1306

1307

Corollary 6.4. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if and only if it’s a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

1308

1309

1310

Corollary 6.5. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor if and only if it’s a longest SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

1311

1312

1313

1314

Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and reversely.

1315

1316

1317

Corollary 6.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and reversely.

Corollary 6.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor isn't well-defined.

Corollary 6.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined.

Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined.

Corollary 6.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Neighbor is well-defined.

Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then V is

- (i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is

- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1359

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1360
1361

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1362

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1363

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1364

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1365

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1366

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1367

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1368
1369
1370

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1371

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1372

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1373

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1374

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1375

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1376

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1377

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1378
1379

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1380

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1381

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1382

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1383

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1384

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1385

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1386

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Neighbor/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1387
1388
1389

(i) : the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1390

(ii) : the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1391

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1392

(iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1393

(v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1394

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1395

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1396
1397

Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1398
1399

(i) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1400

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1401

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1402

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1403

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1404

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1405

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1406
1407

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1408
1409
1410
1411
1412

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1413

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1414

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1415

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1416

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1417

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1418

Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1419
1420
1421
1422
1423
1424

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1425

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1426

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1427

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1428

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1429

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1430

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1435

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1436

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1437

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1438

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1439

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1440

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1441
1442
1443
1444

Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual 1445
1446

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1447

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1448

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1449

(iv) : SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1450

(v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1451

(vi) : connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1452

Proposition 6.25. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Neutrosophic number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$. 1453
1454

Proposition 6.26. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E)) \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual 1455
1456
1457

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1458

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1459

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1460

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1461

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1462

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1463

Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Neutrosophic number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual 1464
1465
1466

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1467

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1468

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1469

(iv) : *0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1470

(v) : *strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1471

(vi) : *connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*. 1472

Proposition 6.28. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.* 1473
1474

Proposition 6.29. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Neighbor/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual* 1475
1476
1477
1478

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1479

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1480

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1481

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1482

(v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1483

(vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*. 1484

Proposition 6.30. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sum_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual* 1485
1486
1487
1488

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1489

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1490

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1491

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1492

(v) : *strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*; 1493

(vi) : *connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor*. 1494

Proposition 6.31. *Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs.* 1495
1496
1497
1498
1499

Proposition 6.32. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that* 1500
1501
1502

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1503

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1504

Proposition 6.33. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then* 1505
1506

(i) S is SuperHyperStable-Neighbor set; 1507

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1508

Proposition 6.34. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then* 1509
1510

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1511

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1512

Proposition 6.35. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then* 1513
1514

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1515

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1516

Proposition 6.36. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then* 1517

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1518
1519

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1520

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1521

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1522
1523

Proposition 6.37. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then* 1524

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1525
1526

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1527
1528

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1529

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1530
1531

Proposition 6.38. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Then* 1532

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1533
1534

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1535
1536

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1537

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1538
1539

Proposition 6.39. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Then* 1540

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1541
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1542
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1543
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1544

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1545

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1546
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1547
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1548
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1549

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1550

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1551
- (ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1552
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)$; 1553
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1554

Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1555

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1556
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$; 1557
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$; 1558
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1559

Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1560

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1561
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1562
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1563
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1564

Proposition 6.44. Let $NSHF : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStars with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1565

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1575
1576
- (ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1577
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1578
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1579
1580

Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1581
1582
1583

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1584
1585
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1586
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1587
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1588
1589

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1590
1591
1592

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1593
1594
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1595
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1596
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Neighbor for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1597
1598

Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1599
1600

- (i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1601
1602
1603
- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1604
1605
1606

Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1607
1608

- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1609
1610
1611
- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1612
1613
1614

Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a[an] 1615
 $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$. Then following 1616
statements hold; 1617

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 1618
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1619
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1620
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1621
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V-SuperHyperDefensive 1622
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1623
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1624
V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1625

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] 1626
 $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$. Then following 1627
statements hold; 1628

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive 1629
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1630
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1631
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1632
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V-SuperHyperDefensive 1633
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1634
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1635
V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1636

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] 1637
 $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is a 1638
SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1639

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive 1640
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1641
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1642
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1643
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive 1644
SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1645
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1646
 $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1647

Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] 1648
 $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is a 1649
SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1650

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 1651
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1652
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1653
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1654
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is 1655
 $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor; 1656

- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Then following statements hold;

- (i) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iii) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Proposition 6.54. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. Then following statements hold;

- (i) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor;
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

7 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. 1700
1701
1702
1703
1704
1705
1706
1707
1708

8 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel 1709 1710 1711

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. 1712
1713
1714
By using the Neutrosophic Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. 1715
1716
The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (29), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. 1717
1718
1719
1720

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor

9 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (30), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor.

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperStable-Neighbor, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperStable-Neighbor and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are

formally called “ SuperHyperStable-Neighbor” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperStable-Neighbor	
3. Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Neighbor	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the

Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients
defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its
Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is
a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge.
Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge
has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 ,
is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges
but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that
there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic

SuperHyperDuality.

1898

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1899

1900

1901

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1902

1903

1904

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1905

1906

1907

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1908

1909

1910

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1911

1912

1913

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1914
1915
1916

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1917
1918
1919

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1920
1921
1922

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1923
1924
1925

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1926
1927
1928

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1929
1930
1931

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1932
1933
1934

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1935
1936
1937

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1938
1939
1940

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1941
1942
1943

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1944
1945
1946

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1947
1948
1949

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1950
1951
1952

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1953
1954
1955

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1956
1957
1958

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 1959
1960

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

1961
1962

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1963

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1964
1965

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

1966
1967
1968

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

1969
1970
1971

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

1972
1973

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then*

1997
1998

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}, \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1999

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

2000
2001

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2002
2003
2004
2005
2006
2007

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any

2008
2009
2010

solution

2011

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

2012

Example 12.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality. 2013
2014
2015
2016
2017
2018

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 2019
2020

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2021

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2022
2023

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 2024
2025

straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
 There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
 minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any
 solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.
 The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic
 result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27),
 is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

13 Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

2082
2083
2084
2085
2086
2087
2088
2089
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin;

2090
2091
2092
2093
2094
2095
2096
2097
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

2098
2099
2100
2101
2102
2103
2104
2105
2106
2107
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

2108
2109
2110
2111
2112
2113
2114
2115
2116
2117
2118
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

2119
2120
2121
2122
2123
2124
2125
2126
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

2127
2128
2129
2130
2131

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; 2132
2133
2134

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2135
2136
2137
2138
2139
2140
2141
2142
2143
2144

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. 2145
2146
2147
2148
2149
2150
2151
2152
2153
2154
2155

Example 13.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 2156
2157

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2158
2159
2160
2161
2162
2163
2164
2165
2166
2167

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus 2168
2169
2170
2171
2172
2173
2174

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2175
2176

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2177
2178
2179

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2180
2181
2182

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2183
2184
2185

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2186
2187
2188

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2189
2190
2191

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2192
2193
2194

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2195
2196
2197

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2198
2199
2200

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2201
2202
2203

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2204
2205
2206

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i \neq 5,7,8}^{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2207
2208
2209

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2210
2211
2212

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2213
2214
2215

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2216
2217
2218

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2219
2220
2221

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2222
2223
2224

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2225
2226
2227

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2228
2229
2230

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2231
2232
2233

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2234
2235
2236

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2237
2238

Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$P :$

$V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$

$V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2,$

$\dots,$

$E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2284

2285

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

2286

2287

2288

2289

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

2290

Example 13.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

2291

2292

2293

2294

2295

2296

Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

2297

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2307

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

2308

2309

2310

2311

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

2312

2313

Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

2314

2315

2316

2317

2318

2319

Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

2320

2321

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

2322

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

14 Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

2360
2361
2362
2363
2364
2365
2366
2367

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

2368
2369
2370
2371
2372
2373
2374
2375

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

2376
2377
2378
2379
2380
2381
2382
2383
2384
2385

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

2386
2387
2388
2389
2390
2391
2392
2393
2394
2395
2396

- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

2397
2398
2399
2400
2401
2402
2403
2404

- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

2405
2406
2407
2408
2409

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2453
2454

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2455
2456
2457

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2458
2459
2460

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2461
2462
2463

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2464
2465
2466

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2467
2468
2469

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2470
2471
2472

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2473
2474
2475

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2476
2477
2478

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2479
2480
2481

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2482
2483
2484

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2485
2486
2487

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2488
2489
2490

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2491
2492
2493

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2494
2495
2496

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2497
2498
2499

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2500
2501
2502

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2503
2504
2505

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=03}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=05}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2506
2507
2508

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2509
2510
2511

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2512
2513
2514

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2515
2516

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

2517

2518

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

2519

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

2520

2521

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

2522

2523

2524

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect.

2525

2526

2527

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

2528

2529

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be

applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 2568

Example 14.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 & = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2585

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

2586

2587

2588

2589

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

2590

2591

Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

2592

2593

2594

2595

2596

2597

Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

2598

2599

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

2600

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

2601

2602

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

2603

2604

2605

2606

2607

2608

Example 14.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$, $\exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$, $\exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}$, $\exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}$, $\exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

2654
2655
2656
2657
2658
2659
2660
2661
2662
2663
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

2664
2665
2666
2667
2668
2669
2670
2671
2672
2673
2674
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

2675
2676
2677
2678
2679
2680
2681
2682
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

2683
2684
2685
2686
2687
2688
2689
2690
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

2691
2692
2693
2694
2695
2696
2697
2698
2699
2700
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a

2701
2702
2703

Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2736
2737
2738

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2739
2740
2741

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2742
2743
2744

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2745
2746
2747

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2748
2749
2750

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly 2751
2752

straightforward.

2753

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2754

2755

2756

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2757

2758

2759

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2760

2761

2762

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2763

2764

2765

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2766

2767

2768

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2769
2770
2771

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2772
2773
2774

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2775
2776
2777

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2778
2779
2780

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2781
2782
2783

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2784
2785
2786

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2787
2788
2789

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2790
2791
2792

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2793
2794

Proposition 15.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 2795
2796

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2797

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &\quad \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} V_i^{EXTERNAL} |_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

2854

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

2855

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

2856

2857

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} & \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

2858

2859

2860

2861

2862

2863

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

2864

2865

2866

2867

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

2868

2869

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

16 Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected** if 2901
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2902
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ 2903
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected** if 2904
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2905
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ and 2906
 $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2907
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected** if 2908
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such 2909
that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ 2910
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected** if 2911
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a;$ $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that 2912
 $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and 2913
 $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2914
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2915
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2916
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected. 2917

Definition 16.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperConnected). 2918

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 2919
a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 2920

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2921
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2922
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 2923
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 2924
Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 2925
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of 2926
Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 2927
the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; 2928
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2929
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2930
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 2931
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 2932
Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic 2933
SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic 2934
SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 2935
Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; 2936
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either 2937
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, 2938
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic 2939
rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph 2940
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme 2941
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality 2942
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high 2943
Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme 2944
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and 2945
the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2946

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

2947
2948
2949
2950
2951
2952
2953
2954
2955
2956
2957

- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

2958
2959
2960
2961
2962
2963
2964
2965

- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

2966
2967
2968
2969
2970
2971
2972
2973

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

2974
2975
2976
2977
2978
2979
2980
2981
2982
2983
2984

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

2985
2986
2987
2988
2989
2990
2991
2992
2993
2994
2995

Example 16.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3023
3024
3025

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3026
3027
3028

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3029
3030
3031

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3032
3033
3034

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3035
3036
3037

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^{19}, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 3038
3039

straightforward.

3040

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

3041

3042

3043

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

3044

3045

3046

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

3047

3048

3049

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

3050

3051

3052

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

3053

3054

3055

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3056
3057
3058

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3059
3060
3061

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3062
3063
3064

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3065
3066
3067

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3068
3069
3070

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3071
3072
3073

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3074
3075
3076

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 3077
3078

Proposition 16.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 3079
3080

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 3081

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 3082
3083

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESH S : (V, E)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}^z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| = \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_b^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_j^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} (|P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i| E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and

SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022),“(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in

Ref. [19] by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [102]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [103]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [104]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [105]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [108]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [109]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [112]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [115]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [116]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [117]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [118]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [119]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [120]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [131]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in **Ref. [132]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–57, 59–132], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph.

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [133]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic

Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [134]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–57, 59–132]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [133, 134].

References

1. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Co-degree and Neutrosophic Degree alongside Chromatic Numbers in the Setting of Some Classes Related to Neutrosophic Hypergraphs*”, J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 1(1) (2022) 06-14.
2. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09)
3. Henry Garrett, “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (<https://www.opastpublishers.com/open-access-articles/some-super-hyper-degrees-and-cosuper-hyper-degrees-on-neutrosophic-super-hyper-graphs-and-super-hyper-graphs-alongside-a.pdf>)
4. Garrett, Henry. “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>
5. Garrett, Henry. “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>
6. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of*

- (*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3355
3356
7. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3357
3358
3359
3360
8. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 3361
3362
3363
9. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3364
3365
3366
3367
3368
3369
10. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3370
3371
3372
3373
11. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3374
3375
3376
3377
12. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3378
3379
3380
3381
13. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3382
3383
3384
14. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3385
3386
3387
3388
15. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3389
3390
3391
16. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3392
3393
3394
17. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3395
3396
3397
3398

18. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3399
3400
3401
3402
19. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3403
3404
3405
20. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3406
3407
3408
3409
3410
21. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3411
3412
3413
22. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3414
3415
3416
3417
23. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3418
3419
3420
3421
24. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 3422
3423
3424
25. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 3425
3426
3427
26. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 3428
3429
3430
27. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 3431
3432
3433
28. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 3434
3435
3436
29. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 3437
3438
3439
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 3440
3441
3442

31. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 3443
3444
3445
32. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 3446
3447
3448
33. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 3449
3450
3451
34. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 3452
3453
3454
35. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 3455
3456
3457
36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 3458
3459
3460
37. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 3461
3462
3463
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 3464
3465
3466
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 3467
3468
3469
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 3470
3471
3472
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 3473
3474
3475
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 3476
3477
3478
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 3479
3480
3481
44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 3482
3483
3484
45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 3485
3486
3487

46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 3488
3489
3490
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 3491
3492
3493
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 3494
3495
3496
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 3497
3498
3499
50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 3500
3501
3502
51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 3503
3504
3505
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 3506
3507
3508
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 3509
3510
3511
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 3512
3513
3514
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 3515
3516
3517
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 3518
3519
3520
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 3521
3522
3523
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 3524
3525
3526
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 3527
3528
3529
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 3530
3531
3532

61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 3533
3534
3535
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 3536
3537
3538
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 3539
3540
3541
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 3542
3543
3544
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 3545
3546
3547
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 3548
3549
3550
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 3551
3552
3553
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 3554
3555
3556
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 3557
3558
3559
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 3560
3561
3562
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 3563
3564
3565
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 3566
3567
3568
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 3569
3570
3571
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 3572
3573
3574
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 3575
3576
3577

76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 3578
3579
3580
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 3581
3582
3583
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 3584
3585
3586
79. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 3587
3588
3589
3590
80. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 3591
3592
3593
3594
81. Henry Garrett, “New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 3595
3596
3597
3598
82. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 3599
3600
3601
3602
83. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 3603
3604
3605
3606
84. Henry Garrett, “A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 3607
3608
3609
3610
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 3611
3612
3613
3614
86. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 3615
3616
3617
87. Henry Garrett, “Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 3618
3619
3620
88. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 3621
3622
3623

89. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 3624
3625
3626
3627
90. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 3628
3629
3630
3631
91. Henry Garrett, “The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 3632
3633
3634
3635
3636
92. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 3637
3638
3639
3640
3641
93. Henry Garrett, “Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 3642
3643
3644
3645
94. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 3646
3647
3648
95. Henry Garrett, “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 3649
3650
3651
3652
96. Henry Garrett, “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 3653
3654
3655
3656
97. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 3657
3658
3659
98. Henry Garrett, “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 3660
3661
3662
3663
3664
3665
99. Henry Garrett, “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 3666
3667
3668
3669

100. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 3670-3673
101. Henry Garrett, “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 3674-3677
102. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 3678-3680
103. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 3681-3684
104. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3685-3688
105. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 3689-3692
106. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 3693-3696
107. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3697-3699
108. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 3700-3702
109. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 3703-3706
110. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 3707-3710
111. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 3711-3714

112. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 3715
3716
3717
3718
113. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 3719
3720
3721
114. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 3722
3723
3724
115. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 3725
3726
3727
116. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 3728
3729
3730
117. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 3731
3732
3733
118. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 3734
3735
3736
3737
119. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 3738
3739
3740
120. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 3741
3742
3743
3744
121. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 3745
3746
3747
122. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 3748
3749
3750
123. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 3751
3752
3753
3754
3755
124. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 3756
3757
3758
3759
3760

125. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 3761
3762
3763
126. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 3764
3765
3766
127. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 3767
3768
3769
3770
128. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 3771
3772
3773
3774
129. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 3775
3776
3777
3778
130. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 3779
3780
3781
3782
131. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 3783
3784
3785
132. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 3786
3787
3788
3789
133. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”, Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United States. ISBN: 979-1-59973-725-6 3790
3791
3792
(<http://fs.unm.edu/BeyondNeutrosophicGraphs.pdf>). 3793
134. Henry Garrett, (2022). “*Neutrosophic Duality*”, Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. ISBN: 978-1-59973-743-0 3794
3795
3796
(<http://fs.unm.edu/NeutrosophicDuality.pdf>). 3797